

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND IN-VITRO EVALUATION OF OSELTAMIVIR PHOSPHATE LOADED NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Nanoparticles, defined as particulate systems with dimensions ranging from 10- 1000nm, have emerged as highly versatile carriers for drug delivery, diagnostics, and therapeutic applications. Depending on their structural design, nanoparticles can exist as nanospheres- where drugs are uniformly dispersed within the matrix – or nano capsules, where drugs are confined within a polymeric cavity surrounded by a membrane. Advances in biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles, particularly those coated with hydrophilic polymers such as polyethylene glycol (PEG), have enabled prolonged circulation, site- specific targeting, and improved delivery of proteins, peptides, nucleic acids, and chemotherapeutic agents. Their preparation involves diverse methods including emulsion – solvent evaporation, double emulsion, salting out, solvent displacement, and diffusion techniques, each influencing particle size, zeta potential, morphology, crystallinity, entrapment efficiency, and in vitro release studies are critical for ensuring reproducibility and

therapeutic efficacy. Nanoparticles find extensive applications across biomedical and pharmaceutical domains, including tumour targeting via passive and active mechanisms, oral and ocular drug delivery, dermatology, pulmonary delivery, gene therapy, molecular diagnostics, and biosensor. Their ability to enhance solubility, protect liable drugs from degradation, and provide sustained or controlled release make them attractive alternatives to conventional dosage forms. However, challenges such as physical instability, reactivity, aggregation, burst release, and limit drug loading remain. Moreover, nanoparticles high reactivity in cellular environments raises safety and stability concerns and further optimization of formulation strategies and materials.

KEYWORDS Nanopartilces, Types of Nanopartilces, Application, Materials and Methods.

INTRODUCTION OF NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles are defined as particulate dispersions or solids particles with a size in the range of 10-1000nm. The drug is dissolved, entrapped, encapsulated or attached to a nano-particle matrix. Depending upon the method of preparation, nanoparticles, nano-spheres or nano capsules can be obtained. Nano-capsules are system in which the drug is confined to a cavity surrounded by a unique polymer membrane, while nano-spheres are matrix system in which the drug is physically and uniformly dispersed. In recent years, biodegradable polymeric nanoparticles, particularly those coated with hydrophilic polymer such as poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) know as long-circulating particles, have been used as potential drug delivery devices because of their ability to circulate for a prolonged period time target a particular organ, as carrier of DNA in gene therapy, and their ability to deliver proteins, peptides and genes. The major goals in designing nanoparticles as a delivery system are to control particle size, surface properties and release of pharmacologically active agents in order to achieve the site-specific action of the drug at the therapeutically optimal rate and dose regimen.

CLASSIFICATION OF NANOPARTICLES

In general, there are three types of nanoparticle: organic, inorganic, and carbon based nanoparticles.

ORGANIC NANOPARTICLES

Ferritin, liposomes, dendrimers, and other organic nanoparticles or polymers are well-known examples. These nanoparticles are non-toxic and biodegradable, yet some, like micelles and liposomes, have a hollow core and are susceptible to electromagnetic and thermal radiation, including heat.

INORGANIC NANOPARTICLES

Non-carbon based particles known as inorganic nanoparticles are often defined as those based on metal and metal oxides.

1. Metal nanoparticles
2. Metal oxides based nanoparticles

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CARBON BASED NANOPARTICLES

There are two main categories of carbon-based NPs: fullerenes and carbon nanotubes (CNTs). Fullerenes contain nanomaterials composed of globular hollow cages, such as allotropic forms of carbon.

Because of their excellent strength, structure, electron affinity, electrical conductivity, adaptability. These materials have sp^2 hybridized carbon units organized in both pentagonal and hexagonal configurations.

1. Fullerene
2. Graphene
3. Carbon nano tube
4. Carbon nano fibres
5. Carbon black

LIMITATIONS

1. Physical handling of nanoparticle is difficult due to small size and large surface area, and also chance of particle-particle aggregation it is due to alteration in physical properties of nanoparticle.
2. In cellular environment nanoparticles are very reactive because of small particle size and great surface area.

3. Burst release and drug loading is limited because of small particle size. These practical problems have to be removed before nanoparticles can be used clinically or made commercially available.

ADVANTAGES

1. Active and passive targeting can be achieved by manipulating the particles size, and surface characteristics of nanoparticles.
2. Surface of the nanoparticles can be modified to alter bio distribution of the drug with subsequent clearance of the drug to get maximum side effects of the drug.
3. Particle degradation characteristics and controlled release can be easily modulated by the choice of matrix constituents.
4. Drug can be incorporated in to the system without any chemical reaction, and also drug loading is relatively high.
5. By attaching targeting ligand to surface of particle or use of magnetic guidance, specific site of targeting can be achieved.
6. Polymer based nanoparticles do not accumulate in the body because used polymer are biodegradable, reduce the possibility of risk.
7. Nanoparticles can penetrate through smaller capillaries due to small size which could allow efficient drug release at the target site.
8. Nanoparticles can be delivered through various routes like oral, nasal, parenteral, and intraocular etc.

DISADVANTAGES

1. High cost.
2. Highly sophisticated technology.
3. Difficult to maintain stability of dosage form.
4. Requires skills to manufacturer.
5. Susceptable to bursting and leakage of drug content.

APPLICATIONS OF NANOPARTICLES

1. Nanoparticles as a drug delivery system for peptides and proteins

Solid lipid nano-particles(SLN), lipid microparticles (LM)and lipospheres have been sought as alternative carriers for therapeutic peptides, proteins, and antigens.

2. Tumor targeting delivery systems

Nanoparticles will be able to deliver a concentrate dose of drug in the vicinity of the tumor targets via the enhanced permeability and retention effect or active targeting by ligands on the surface of nanoparticles.

3. Nanoparticles in dermatology

Drug delivery to skin by means of microparticles and nanocarriers could revolutionize the treatment of several skin disorders

4. Nanoparticle in cosmetics

In particular, NLCs have been identified as a potential next generation cosmetic delivery agent that can provide enhanced skin hydration, bioavailability, stability of the agent and controlled occlusion.

5. Nanoparticle for gene delivery

Nucleic acids can be loaded onto GNPs through physical encapsulation, electrostatic attraction or complexation with surface modifying groups were the first to develop type B GNPs as noncondensing gene delivery systems.

6. Nanoparticles in ocular delivery systems

The lipids of SLN are easy to metabolize and open a new ways for ophthalmological drug delivery without impairing vision.

7. Nanoparticles as per-oral drug delivery

Increased bioavailability and prolonged plasma levels have been described after per oral administration of cyclosporine containing lipid nano dispersions to animals.

8. Implantable delivery systems

Intraperitoneal application of drug-loaded SLN will prolong the release because of the application area. In addition, incorporation of the drug into SLN might reduce irritancy compared to injecting drug micro particles.

9. Nanoparticles as pulmonary drug delivery

This basically demonstrates that SLN are suitable for lung delivery. After localization into the bronchial tube and in the alveoli, the drug can be released in a controlled way from the lipid particles.

10. Nanoparticle in Molecular diagnostics

Nanoparticles used in magnetic resonance imaging, optical imaging, ultrasonic imaging and nuclear imaging.

11. Nanoparticle as Biosensor and bio-labels

A Nano biosensor or nano-sensor is a biosensor that has dimensions on the nano-meter size scale. Biosensors are used in target identification, validation, assay development, ADME, toxicity determination.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Raw materials

S. NO	NAME OF THE MATERILAS	NAME OF THE SUPPLIERS
1	Oseltamivir phosphate	Solara Active Pharma Science Limited
2	Dichloromethane	LABINDIA
3	Eudragit	LABINDIA
4	Polyvinyl alcohol	LABINIDA

Equipments

S.NO	EQUIPMENT	MANUFACTURER/SUPPLIERS
1.	Electronic weighing balance	Wensar
2.	Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy	SHIMADZU
3.	UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Labindia-UV 3000
4.	Melting Point Apparatus	Guna Enterprises, madras
5.	Magnetic stirrer	Remi Equipment
6.	High speed centrifuge	Remi equipment
7.	Scanning electron microscope	Hitachi, Japan
8.	Particle size analyzer	Malvern Instrument
9.	Dissolution test apparatus	Labindia
10.	Hot air oven	Labtech Instrument
11.	Stability chamber	Labtech Instrument
12.	pH meter	Infra Digi Equipment
13.	Zeta sizer	Horiba Scientific
14.	Disintegration test apparatus	Remi Instrument

Methodology Formulation studies

Identification of drug by FTIR Spectroscopy

FTIR study was carried out to identify the drug. Infrared spectrum of Oseltamivir Phosphate was determined on Fourier transform Infrared Spectroscopy using KBr dispersion method.

The base line correction was done using dried potassium bromide. Then the spectrum of dried mixture of drug and potassium bromide was performed by using FTIR spectrophotometer. The absorption maximum in spectrum obtained with the substance being examined corresponding position and relative intensity to those in the reference spectrum.

Determination of melting point

A small amount of drug was loaded in a capillary tube where one of capillary tube was closed and kept in the melting point apparatus and temperature was noted when drug melts.

Organoleptic Properties

The colour and odour of the drug were recorded using descriptive terminology.

Determination of λ max

Weighed 25 mg of oseltamivir phosphate in 25 ml of volumetric flask and diluted with Dimethyl formamide (to soluble the drug) to get 1 mg/ml concentration solution. From the stock solution taken 5 ml of solution in 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted with distilled water to get 50 μ g/ml solution. The solution was then scanned at 200-400 nm in UV – Visible spectrometer to attain the absorption maximum (λ max).

Development of Standard curve of Oseltamivir phosphate**Preparation of pH 7.4 buffer**

8gm of sodium chloride was dissolved in 1000ml of distilled water then added 0.2g of potassium chloride in 1.44g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate. The pH was adjusted with 0.1N hydrochloric acid or 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

Preparation of Stock Solution of Oseltamivir Phosphate in pH 7.4 Phosphate buffer saline

Weighed 50gm of Oseltamivir in 100ml volumetric flask. Make up the volume with phosphate buffer saline pH 7.4. 10ml of stock solution was pipette out with 100ml volumetric flask make up the volume with phosphate buffer saline. The solution was diluted to 50 μ g/ml. From the secondary stock solution take 1,2,3,4 & 5ml of solution in 10ml volumetric flask & diluted with buffer solution to get 5,10,15,20,25 μ g/ml solution. Scanned in UV spectrometer at 214nm.

Drug – Excipient Compatibility Study

The possibilities of drug – excipient (lipid and surfactant) interactions were investigated by FT- IR spectrum study. The FT-IR spectrum of pure drug with excipient were recorded using Shimadzu FT-IR spectrophotometer. The spectrum was recorded in the wavelength region of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . The IR spectra of the test sample were obtained by Pressed Pellet Technique using Potassium bromide.

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF OSELTAMIVIR PHOSPHATE LOADED NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles are prepared by polymers like polyvinyl alcohol, eudragit, ethyl cellulose by solvent evaporation method. Disperse phase consisting of Oseltamivir phosphate (100mg) and requisite quantity of polymers dissolved in 20ml solvent (dichloromethane) was slowly added to a definite amount of PVA in 100ml of aqueous continuous phase. This mixture was stirred at 1000 rpm for two – three hours on a magnetic stirrer. The nanoparticles formed were collected by filtration through whatman filter paper dried in oven at 50°C for 2 hours. The dried nanoparticles were stored in vacuum desiccator to ensure the removal of residual solvent.

Formulation	Oseltamivir phosphate (mg)	Ethyl cellulose (mg)	Eudragit (mg)	Polyvinyl alcohol (in mg)	Dichloro methane (ml)	Distilled water (ml)
1	75	200	-	0.2	20	100
2	75	400	-	0.2	20	100
3	75	600	-	0.2	20	100
4	75	-	200	0.2	20	100
5	75	-	400	0.2	20	100
6	75	-	600	0.2	20	100

Characterization of Oseltamivir phosphate-loaded nanoparticles Entrapment efficiency

The entrapment efficiency (EE) of Oseltamivir Phosphate-loaded nanoparticles was determined by measuring the amount of unentrapped drug present in the supernatant after centrifugation. A known quantity of nanoparticle dispersion was centrifuged at 5000 RPM for 15 minutes. The supernatant was collected and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 258 nm to estimate free drug.

$$\text{Entrapment efficiency} = \frac{\text{Total drug taken} - \text{Free drug}}{\text{Total drug taken}} \times 100$$

FTIR Spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy was used to study possible interactions between Oseltamivir Phosphate and the excipients, as well as to confirm the presence of the drug in the nanoparticles. The spectra were recorded using the KBr pellet method. The characteristic absorption peaks of the optimized formulation were compared with those of the pure drug to verify the retention of structural integrity and compatibility with the lipid matrix

Drug Content

To determine drug content, 50 mg of Oseltamivir Phosphate-loaded nanoparticles was dissolved in 50 ml of chloroform. The dispersion was shaken to ensure complete drug extraction, filtered, and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 258 nm using chloroform as blank.

$$\text{Percentage drug content} = \frac{\text{Drug content}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM was performed to examine the **surface morphology** of the prepared nanoparticles. The SEM images provided information regarding particle shape, surface smoothness, and aggregation behavior.

Particle Size and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

Particle size and PDI of the Oseltamivir Phosphate-loaded nanoparticles were measured using **Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)** with a Malvern Zetasizer Nano S at 25°C. Samples were diluted with ultrapure water to achieve suitable scattering intensity, then transferred into disposable cuvettes for analysis. Air bubbles were removed before measurement. A **low PDI value** indicates a uniform (monodisperse) distribution, while a **high PDI** indicates polydispersity.

$$PDI = d/d \text{ avg}$$

Where

- d is the width of distribution denoted by SD,
- $d \text{ avg}$ is the average particle size denoted by MV (nm) in particle size data sheet.

Zeta potential

The zeta potential is an important parameter that determines the electric charge present on the surface of nanoparticles. It is a key indicator of the physical stability of colloidal systems. The zeta potential values of the Oseltamivir Phosphate– loaded nanoparticles were measured to assess their surface charge and overall stability. A 1 ml sample of the Oseltamivir Phosphate–loaded nanoparticle dispersion was transferred into a clear disposable zeta cell, ensuring no air bubbles were present. The measurement was carried out using a Malvern Zetasizer at a controlled temperature of 25 °C, and the results were recorded. A higher magnitude of negative zeta potential indicates a greater net surface charge on the nanoparticles, which corresponds to enhanced electrostatic repulsion between particles and improved stability of the nanoparticle formulation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Formulation study

It is an investigation of the physical, chemical and mechanical properties of a drug substance to develop a safe, effective and stable dosage form. It is the first step in rational development of dosage form.

Identification of drug

- Identification of oseltamivir phosphate by FTIR spectroscopy

The characteristic peaks of functional groups present in the drugs were checked and depicted in Table 6.1. The functional groups present in the structure of oseltamivir phosphate were identified correctly and hence the drugs was confirmed and considered for further uses.

Compound	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	Types of Vibration
Oseltamivir phosphate	3163.26	N-H stretching
	2877.79	C-H stretching
	1728.22	C=O stretching
	1666.50	C=O (amide) stretching
	1465.90	CH ₂ bending
	1373.32	CH ₃ bending
	1550.77	Amide II bending

Identification of melting point

The melting point of oseltamivir phosphate was determined by using melting point Apparatus.

S. NO.	Melting point	Concordant value
1	202 °C	206 °C
2	204°C	
3	213°C	

Physiochemical properties of drug

● Solubility of Osteltamivir phosphate

The solubility of oseltamivir phosphate was determined by a semi quantitative method.

water : freely soluble

Methanol : freely soluble

Chloroform : soluble

0.1N Hcl : soluble

0.1N NaoH : soluble

Dichloromethane : freely soluble

● Organoleptic properties

Odour : odourless

Colur : white crystalline powder.

Preparation of standard curve of oseltamivir phosphate in distilled water						
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0	5	10	15	20	25
Absorbance	0	0.123	0.232	0.348	0.48	0.61

Preparation of standard curve of oseltamivir phosphate in pH 7.4 Phosphate buffer Saline

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0	5	10	15	20	25
Absorbance	0	0.139	0.269	0.356	0.458	0.619

Compound	Frequency (cm^{-1})	Types of vibration
Oseltamivir phosphate with ethyl cellulose	3456.44	O-H stretching
	3348.42	N-H stretching
	1720.50	C=O stretching
	1373.32	CH ₃ bending
	1442.75	O-H bending

CHARACTERIZATION OF OSELATMIVIR PHOSPHATE LOADED NANOPARTICLES

Determination of Entrapment efficiency

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Percentage entrapment efficiency	99.99	99.98	99.97	99.99	99.98	99.97

Determination of drug content

Formulation code	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Percentage of drug content	99.99	99.98	99.97	99.99	99.98	99.97

Determination of in-vitro drug release

Time (in Hrs)	Absorbance	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount Found	% Drug Release
1	0.042	0.81	7.25	9.59
2	0.067	1.89	17.04	22.54
3	0.097	3.20	28.79	38.09
4	0.124	4.37	39.36	52.08
5	0.137	4.94	44.45	58.82
6	0.158	5.85	52.68	69.71
7	0.197	7.55	67.95	89.92
8	0.219	8.51	76.57	101.32

Morphology of Oseltamivir phosphate nanoparticles by Scanning Electron Microscopy Analysis(SEM)

Inference

SEM image of oseltamivir phosphate nanoparticles loaded capsule was recorded. The particles are almost spherical and homogeneous. The results show that the oseltamivir phosphate have a spherical shape with smooth surface and discrete without any aggregation or agglomeration.

Determination of particle size and polydispersity of optimized formulation

Size Distribution Report by Intensity

v2.1

Sample Details

Sample Name: Vigneshwar
SOP Name: mansettings.nano
General Notes:

File Name: Particle size and Zeta.dts Dispersant Name: Water
Record Number: 1614 Dispersant PE: 1.330
Material PE: 1.59 Viscosity (cP): 0.8872
Material Absorption: 0.010 Measurement Date and Time: December 13, 2025 11:23...

System

Temperature (°C): 25.0 Duration Used (s): 80
Count Rate (kcps): 167.0 Measurement Position (mm): 4.65
Cell Description: Disposable sizing cuvette Attenuator: 11

Results

	Size (d.nm):	% Intensity	Width (d.nm)
Z-Average (d.nm):	607.5	100.0	84.70
PDI:	1.000	0.0	0.000
Intercept:	0.730	0.0	0.000
Peak 1:	532.6		
Peak 2:	0.000		
Peak 3:	0.000		

Result quality : Refer to quality report

Inference

The particle size and polydispersity of F4 formulation was found to be 607.5 nm and 1.000.

Determination of zeta potential of F4 formulation Inference

The Zeta potential for the F4 formulation was found to be -27.1mv and shows that the formulation is stable.

Zeta Potential Report

v2.2

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Sample Details

Sample Name: Vigneshwar
 SOP Name: mansetingurano
 General Notes:

File Name: Particle size and Zeta.xls Dispersant Name: Water
 Record Number: 1620 Dispersant pH: 1.330
 Date and Time: December 13, 2025 11:44:41 ... Viscosity (cP): 0.8872
 Dispersant Dielectric Constant: 78.5

System

Temperature (°C): 25.0 Zeta Runs: 12
 Count Rate (kcps): 300.5 Measurement Position (mm): 2.00
 Cell Description: Clear disposable zeta cell Attenuator: 6

Results

	Mean (mV)	Area (%)	Width (mV)
Zeta Potential (mV): -27.1	Peak 1: -32.3	59.8	6.92
Zeta Deviation (mV): 9.59	Peak 2: -18.4	40.2	4.41
Conductivity (mS/cm): 2.39	Peak 3: 0.00	0.0	0.00
Result quality : Good			

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this research was to prepare Oseltamivir phosphate loaded nanoparticles for increasing the bioavailability of Oseltamivir phosphate. Oseltamivir phosphate is a poorly soluble drug with the low oral bioavailability, thus selected as a model drug for nanoparticles.

- ❖ Solvent evaporation technique was employed to produce nanoparticles using Dichloromethane, Eudragit and polyvinyl alcohol.
- ❖ The compatibility study of Oseltamivir phosphate with excipients was carried out using FTIR Spectrometer, it revealed no interaction between the drug & excipients.
- ❖ Calibration curve was plotted for Oseltamivir phosphate and it was found that the

solutions show linearity (0.993) and obeyed Beer Lambert's Law

- ❖ The formulation of F-4 loaded nanoparticles was evaluated for FT-IR study and it is clearly evident that the f-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle showed the presence of characteristics bands of oseltamivir phosphate. This indicates the absence of chemical interaction between the drug and the excipients.
- ❖ Entrapment efficiency of the F-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle was determined and its entrapment efficiency was observed to be 99.99 %
- ❖ The F-4 formulation loaded nanoparticles was characterized for surface morphology particle size analysis and zeta potential. The shape and surface morphology of f-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle was observed in scanning electron microscopy. It showed that nanoparticle was spherical and discrete in morphology. The particle size distribution and polydispersity study were carried out using particle size analyzer. The mean particle size of F-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle was found to be 607.5 nm. polydispersity of F-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle was found to be indicating uniformity of particle size within formulation. The zeta potential study was done by Zeta sizer. The zeta potential for the F-4 formulation loaded nanoparticle was found to be - 27.1 mv which showed that the formulation is stable.
- ❖ The F4 formulation was further formulated a capsule.

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